

A report on authentic practices for working with children with English as an additional language

By: Neharika Verma

Table Of Contents

1. Introduction	Page 1
<hr/>	
2. Purpose of the report	Page 1
<hr/>	
3. Background	Page 2
<hr/>	
4. Practices to support children with English as Additional language	Page 2 - 8
<hr/>	
a. Incorporating keywords of child's first language to relate to English	
b. Peer to peer communication	
c. Using music and songs to build communication	
d. Partnerships with whanau	
e. Engaging fluent home language people and bilingual teachers	
<hr/>	
5. Summary and challenges	Page 8-9
<hr/>	
6. References	Page 9-10

Introduction

Early Childhood Education centers and environments are evergrowing with multicultural and multi-linguistic tamariki, whanau, and communities over a large period of time in New Zealand (Song, 2020). With multicultural and multi-linguistic whanau in the centers, early childhood teachers and groups are working hard to support tamariki whose first language is not English. As English is a language that becomes a medium of communication among a diverse range of people with multiple languages and cultures, it is very important to support early learners to build some confidence and knowledge of this language. As much as English is an important language to learn, it is as important to support a child's mana, whanau, and community, provide them a sense of belonging and respect for their own language and cultural knowledge, and values in the learning environment, (Ministry Of Education, 2017). Therefore, it is quite essential for educators to learn, understand and plan programs and strategies that support and uplift bilingual children, especially in building confidence, vocabulary, and practicing the use of the English language.

This short report shall focus on some of the practices that support tamariki with English as their second language with the support of their kaiako. These practices will focus on critical theories, socio-cultural theories, funds of knowledge, hegemony, and commitment to *the Treaty of Waitangi*.

Purpose

This report is written to draw on some practices that have been used by me, noticed, or plan on new strategies and practices based on socio-cultural theories, cultural knowledge, and cultural influences on children. The purpose is to support children and families who might be in need of additional support such as language upskilling or families who face language barrier issues in their children's education and learning. Personally, coming from a family who did not speak English at all, and facing several social, mental, economic, and political barriers because of not understanding the language, it is an extremely relevant and relatable issue to me as an educator because I have the power to support those who face the same issues as me. Therefore this report shall focus on providing support, value, and strategies for non-English speaking communities. To remove language barriers and increase the chances of growth, progress, and success, it is important to focus on this cause.

Background

With over 60 children, set in Glen Eden, Auckland, my early childhood center is divided into 3 rooms: Babies, Toddlers, and Preschoolers with quite a lot of multi-lingual and culturally diverse tamariki and whanau. Most of the families in the center are either Pasifika, Indian, Asian, or Middle-Eastern with quite a lot of families who do not use English as their first language. Quite a lot of staff is also Indian/Asian/Pasifika/Maori. As the center is culturally and linguistically diverse, there are a lot of common practices to ensure that non-English speaking tamariki and whanau understand the routines, customs, plans, and communicate well. I have been working with infants and toddlers who are developing language and communication skills. I am understanding their knowledge funds, how they copy others and grow their own vocabulary and I use this knowledge to support their learning. I have noticed the staff holding monthly and weekly meetings to understand and create plans for such tamariki and learning languages to support their vocabulary and build communicational skills with tamariki.

Practices for working with children with English as an additional language

1. Incorporating keywords of child's first language to relate to English

Te Whāriki reflects that weaving together ideas and different world views is the way to support a child's mana, wellbeing, and growth in an early childhood environment. (Ministry Of Educations, 2017). Weaving children's first language in their daily routines and play and relating the words and phrases to English as their second language will allow them to not only settle in the environment but also develop an understanding of both languages, multiliteracy at the same time.

Krashen (1992) found that children who are more proficient in their home language literacy find it easier to develop literacy in their second language. One of the most common practices used by our teachers, learning keywords from a child's first language is used in our center. In our current practice, we have an 'All about me' book at the center for each child where the whanau and teachers regularly update each other with daily routines, notes, language milestones, and aspirations that are related to the child. Parents use that book as a communication tool to support their child's language by introducing some common words in their language and how the child uses them by writing them down. Teachers have been reading and understanding the words and the meaning behind the terms and using it to have some direct conversations with the child. It has been quite helpful for the child and

the whanau, especially those children who have just arrived at the center and settled in. “Teachers communicate in conscious and unconscious ways and must choose what they illustrate to children with regard to culture, language and therefore the children themselves” (Cummins, 2009). This practice is ensuring that children with bilingual whanau still have access to their language once they leave their houses and that they “experience an environment that values their own and other’s languages and cultures” (Ministry Of Education, 1996, p.78). As infants and toddlers are still developing verbal language, incorporating their first language in their environment creates a sense of balance and avoids the hegemony that one language is better than the other in society. This is beneficial for monolingual tamariki as well as they are exposed to other languages, forms, and sounds, allowing them to understand the different concepts of language and literacy as well as socio-cultural awareness and knowledge. It adds to the funds of knowledge children already possess from socio-cultural interactions with their whanau, community, culture, and nation (Cummins, 2009). “Vygotsky’s socio-cultural ideas state that learning leads the development and occurs in relationships with people, places and things, mediated by participation in valued social and cultural activities” (Ministry Of Education, 2017,p.61).

Learning keywords and phrases is not the only thing that needs attention, but understanding pronunciation, phonology, articulation, structure (grammar) and semantics (meaning) of the words is also important for kaiako. How must a sentence translate to English? It is important to understand and know that to support the child. Furthermore, these terms and words can be incorporated in daily routines, for example: Exchanging “Labaan” in Egyptian for “Milk” in English for an Egyptian child who is still developing English literacy. The parents can support by using English terms for the same action or routine at home, by adding “labaan” with “milk” at home for the same action.

2. Peer to peer communication

Growing children often observe what other children are doing and speaking. I have noticed that during play when one child talks to another child using descriptive talk in English like “catch”, “sit”, “yummy food”, “give me?”, “take it” or “mine” along with actions and doings, other children tend to learn vocabulary and their meanings quicker. The words slowly make sense to children with a demonstration by other children (Ministry Of Education, 2017). Kaiako can support these sorts of

conversations by also introducing new words and demonstrating the meaning behind them.

However there is a fear of English overpowering children whose first language is not English and their own language might diminish from the environment as they engage in English more and more. “For children learning two languages at the same time, the danger is that one language, usually the societally dominant one, becomes the language of greatest proficiency, and the mother tongue is gradually lost” (Bates, 2016, p.11). To eliminate the hegemony of a language in the learning space kaiako can also support bilingual children to introduce some words from their language to other children. Children can be each other’s Tuakana and Teina and have equal opportunities to learn and to teach through their play and language. (Ministry Of Education, 2017). Allowing children to share, not letting them being isolated and overpowered by one language and fostering their culture, identity and language will ensure their growth and eliminate the hegemony of one language and culture over the others. It is also observed that “Children who speak two or more languages grow up in culturally diverse environment and already have a vast store of knowledge” (Beauchamp, 2016, p.25). Supported by Drury in 2013, it is advocated why the Socio-cultural perspective should be used in children’s learning, as learning language, social and cultural interaction is connected to socialization. Expanding their own (children’s) and other’s cultural capital funds through exchange of conversations, having culturally diverse environment for play and learning supports bilingual children’s ability to grow in other languages including English. “Capability in the home language largely determines the capability in all subsequent languages”. (Bialystok, 2007; Cummins, 2007). Kaiako can make sure that there are often spaces and opportunities where all children can share their language and cultural knowledge through communication and actions. Demonstrating English and their languages side by side, for example, “Sit” in English, “Baitho” in Hindi, “E NoHo” in Maori. With time and continuity, children start engaging and leading these conversations and learn along with each other.

Ensuring that all languages and cultural values, especially Te Reo Maori and Tikanga Maori values are well protected and encouraged in the learning environment ensures commitment to the Treaty Of Waitangi. Participation and partnership with our whanau to understand, respect and foster cultural and linguistic values of Maori and multicultural communities is our commitment to guard, protect and support Maori and its values. “Te Reo Māori is a taonga under article two of Te Tiriti o Waitangi. Fostering the learning and use of te reo Māori is the responsibility of all kaiako and the education system as a whole” (Ministry of Education, 2017).

3. Using music and songs to build communication

Music and songs is something that children love to listen to and copy when heard daily. I have often noticed children singing “wheels on the bus along” along with the music when they hear it along with actions on a daily basis. Tamariki with English as second language, who are still learning to make sentences and phrases, often feel confident in singing English songs and rhymes that use actions and demonstration (Beauchamp, 2016). Using songs and rhymes in English to support the development of English language as well as using songs and rhymes from the child’s first language is a very responsive and progressive way of supporting the child’s language and culture and introducing a new language at the same time. This should be accompanied by pictures, actions, and videos. Demonstration, pictorial representation and clear meaning behind words, are important for children to relate to actions.

Anecdotal example: An Egyptian child, newly settled in the center has been developing his English level proficiency and while other children sing and dance to English rhymes, he has been trying to understand what is happening and feels a bit disconnected from others. However, upon playing the same rhyme in Egyptian for the child, he is surprised that someone from his place is singing to him and he looks for them everywhere. He giggles and nods his head in excitement. He recognizes symbols, songs, and things that relate to his culture and language and uses this knowledge to engage in play and extend his learning. As we slowly merge his language and English together for the same rhyme, we have started doing the same actions for the same rhymes. With time, we aim at supporting him in making connections to his language and a new language through music and rhythm. Music is effortless play for children and they enjoy it everytime. This also benefits monolingual English speakers. “Monolingual children also benefit from exposure to other language forms and sound” (Bates, 2016, p. 15). *Te Korero* talks about using music along with gestures, movement and facial expressions to develop language vocabulary and understanding meanings behind the words and phrases (Ministry Of Education, 2017). Even wordless music from one’s culture can be used to create songs, waiatas and rhymes during mat times and play where kaiako can introduce random English words along with the music, for example “turn around, this is my head, e noho, lets sit down”.

It is important that “Toddlers have opportunities for music and movement, including participation in dance and learning skills with musical instruments” (Ministry Of Education, 2017, p.43).

4. Partnerships with whanau

Te Whaariki mentions that “Family and community will contribute knowledge of their children’s capabilities at home and in other settings and will be seen as ‘experts’ on their children’s interests” (Ministry Of Education, 2017, p.64).

Nixon and Gould (1999) encourage strong two-way partnerships with parents and caregivers to develop inclusive curricula and routines for their children. Engaging whanau in developing routines, practicing reciprocal and responsive relationships, and regular communication to notice, respond, and reflect on the needs of the child is important in an early childhood environment (Bates, 2016).

Acquiring cultural knowledge about a child’s culture and community, understanding how English translates to their language, and their own knowledge of the language. Engaging in conversations with whanau that talk about their culture, language, the use of language at home, how much does the child understand and what parent’s aspirations are for the child, and/or having them written down a personalized portfolio or book. *Te Whaariki* emphasizes on the fact that “Kaiako should have a good understanding of the learning that is valued by whānau, hapū, iwi, and community, and this will be reflected in the information that is shared with them” (Ministry Of Education, 2017, p.64).

For groups, like immigrants, or economically poor families, it is a vital requirement that the family’s aspirations, language and cultures are promoted along with a second language that allows success for their children and the overall well-being of the whanau. “Funds of knowledge is an approach to curriculum based on the simple premise that “People are competent, they have knowledge, and their life experiences have given them that knowledge” (Gonzalez, Moll & Amanti 2005, pp. ix-x). Kaiako need to include practices that provide opportunities and equal partnership to whanau, by letting them share their funds of knowledge and valuable experience they bring with them. Sometimes, challenges like cultural differences or linguistic differences that the kaiako might not be aware of, or practices in the center that are not appropriate for the culture of the child, can be customized through conversations with parents and finding out the “appropriate ways” to do certain routines and use certain languages. For example, In Indian culture, one does not say their elder’s name, it is

disrespectful to them, however, Pakeha children are encouraged to say their elder's name,s and sometimes not knowing the names is considered disrespectful. These practices are quite opposite to each other and maybe followed by the teachers, parents or caregivers at the center. Kaiako needs to be aware of these cultural values that link with languages through conversations with whanau. In my opinion, the key to effective partnerships is continuous communication with whanau. "Parents are able to identify the child's 'real' language practices, oral, conceptual and written". (Michael-Luna, 2013).

5. Engaging fluent home language people and bilingual teachers

Having a diverse group of teachers/educators in early childhood education establishes a level of relatability, belongingness, and a broad perspective from different experiences that people bring in. Tamariki finds it easy to settle, connect and learn a language when there is a person present in their environment that understands and relates to their own identity. Ball (2012) in her research mentioned, "that the management and colleagues should support bilingual teachers on languages and literacy development to meet the needs with children from diverse cultures and languages". In research by Song,(2020), it was evident that having bilingual teachers in the center supported tamariki in building a strong foundation for their second language, i.e English as well. "Teachers also believed that children's communication skills, as well as their social and thinking skills that developed with their home languages, will transfer to their host language learning and form a metalinguistic foundation of future language learning" (Issa & Hatt, 2013; MoE, 2010; Nemeth, 2009). Teachers who have multicultural knowledge and experience bring in rich culture, perspectives and life experiences that may be similar to what some children's families have, for example, immigrant teachers and families, teachers speaking certain languages understand phonology and syntax of words and sentences and use that knowledge to support tamariki's first language as well as build a new foundation for a foreign language. It also makes it easier for non-english speaking whanau to feel comfortable and express their opinions, situations, goals and aspirations for the tamariki.

Te Whaariki says that "Children's learning and development is enhanced when culturally appropriate ways of communicating are used and when parents, whānau and community are encouraged to participate in and contribute to the curriculum" (Ministry Of Education, 2017, p.20). This can be achieved by involving parents,

grandparents and whanau who speak tamariki's language to take part in children's learning, planning, activities and conversations. Tamariki's cultural capital and funds of knowledge are quite the foundation for their ways of being, language and dispositions and involving whanau can "Provide cross-over for the child, enabling them to build on prior knowledge through direct reference to their home life". (Cummins, 2009). According to sociocultural theory by Vygotsky, "children's language development is understood as a socio-cultural process which takes place through their participation in their own communities and families" (Song, 2020). Therefore, there should opportunities and setups by kaiako and management that allow multilingual whanau to take part in children's daily lives, sit and talk with them, read our stories and books, hold cultural events and celebrate festivals with them, sing and dance and support settling children with English as an additional language. Valuing multi-lingual and multicultural whanau and kaiako in early childhood is a requirement and contributes to the commitment to the Treaty of Waitangi by involving whanau in the process, acknowledging and giving equal decision-making power to all the parties involved in the process and those who will be affected.

Summary and Challenges

There are a few challenges that are faced as a teacher in supporting tamariki who are still learning a second language. The first one is not having enough resources or teachers who understand a child's first language. The child may end up feeling out of place and unsettled because there is nobody to understand what he/she is trying to communicate or express. This is a first-hand observation in my working experience where we have felt helpless because of not understanding a child's words or language and not having enough knowledge or resources like stories, books, translation, people who can understand the child. At such times, we have used technology and social media application like youtube to support the child. Therefore, some level of knowledge, training and resources is required to support every child and whanau that come in the learning environment and developing second language knowledge. According to Ministry Of Education, 2017, tamariki's learning is evident when "Confidence that their first language is valued and increasing ability in the use of at least one language" (p.42).

This is a challenge that is commonly faced by a lot of centers and it can only be resolved by more whanau involvement, observations, better planning and most importantly training of teachers. "For teachers to best support children to retain fluent home languages, they must break barriers for themselves, for parents and children, for center culture, and for societal

expectations. They must be better prepared with training in linguistics, the importance of language, and the benefits for multilingual children in New Zealand” (Bates, 2012, p.15)

This report focuses on the development of English for children whose first language is not English. We have looked at the purpose, strategies and a few challenges that are part of this process. We have noticed that children learn a second language better when their home language is acknowledged and supported, allowing them to build a new foundation for a second language. Meanwhile, the involvement of Whanau, teachers and relatable communities that form a child’s social environment is important in developing plans and having ongoing learning at home, at early childhood centers and in the outside world. To achieve this kaikao also requires some training and understanding of different cultures, languages, barriers and devise ways to resolve them and work with whanau closely to achieve a progressive learning process for the child. My own practice has been closely linked to all the strategies I have followed, there are some observations from those practices as mentioned above and some planning that will continuously happen over time and with new situations. My responsibility as an intentional teacher is to intentionally create environments and opportunities using play, music, stories, activities, events, meetings, and planning to support the child’s language and learning in best possible ways. It also involves regular review of my knowledge and training, and updating myself with new information and some context for the child’s benefit. Kaiako should “Include in assessments of program quality information on instructional practices, including the balance of teaching and interactions in each language, as well as the language abilities of staff members” (Matthews, 2011, p.5). As per *Our Codes, Our Standards*, my responsibility is to “design learning based on curriculum and pedagogical knowledge, assessment information and an understanding of each learner’s strengths, interests, needs, identities, languages and cultures” (Education Council New Zealand, 2017).

References

- Ball, C. E. (2012). *The richness diversity brings: Diverse languages and literacies in early childhood education*. (Unpublished Master’s thesis, Auckland University of Technology, Auckland, New Zealand). Retrieved from <http://aut.researchgateway.ac.nz/bitstream/handle/10292/4752/BallCE.pdf>
- Bates, S. (2016). Bilingual children?: Or just pre-schoolers learning English?. *Early Education*, 59, 11-16.

Bialystok, E. (2007). *Cognitive effects of bilingualism: How linguistic experience leads to cognitive change*. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 10(3), 210-223.

Beauchamp, A. K. (2016). Overcoming language barriers in early childhood education. *Unpublished Master's thesis, Massey University, Palmerston North, New Zealand*. Retrieved from <https://mro.massey.ac.nz/handle/10179/8341>.

Cummins, J. (2009). Pedagogies of choice, challenging coercive relations of power in classrooms and communities. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 12(3), 261-271

Drury R. (2013). How silent is the 'Silent Period' for young bilinguals in early years settings in England?, *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 21:3, 380-391, DOI: 10.1080/1350293X.2013.814362

Education Council New Zealand. (2017). *Our code our standards: Code of professional responsibility and standards for the teaching profession*.

Gonzalez, N., Moll, L.C. & Amanti, C. (2005). *Funds of knowledge: Theorizing practices in households, communities, and classrooms*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates

HOHAIA, T. Storytelling and oral language Te kōrero pūrakau me te reo ā-waha. *Talking Together*, 33.

Issa, T., & Hatt, A. (2013). *Language, culture and identity in the early years*. London, England: Bloomsbury Academic.

Krashen, S. (1992). *Fundamentals of language education*. Torrance, CA: Laredo Publishing.

Matthews, H. (2011). Meeting the Early Learning Challenge: Supporting English Language Learners. *Center for Law and Social Policy, Inc.(CLASP)*.

Michael-Luna, S. (2013). What linguistically diverse parents know and how it can help early childhood Educators: A case study of a dual language preschool community. *Early Childhood Education Journal* 41, 447–455

Ministry of Education (2017). NGĀ RAUEMI WHAKAKŌRERO, *Te kōrerorero - Talking together*. New Zealand: Learning Media.

Ministry of Education (1996) *Te Whāriki: He whāriki mātauranga mō ngā mokopuna o Aotearoa. Early childhood curriculum*. Wellington, New Zealand: Learning Media.

Ministry of Education (2010). *The literacy learning progressions: Meeting the reading and writing demands of the curriculum*. Wellington, New Zealand: Author.

Nemeth, K. (2009). *Many languages, one classroom: Teaching dual and English language learners*. Beltsville, MD: Gryphon House.

Song, H. H. (2020). *The Challenges and Benefits of Maintaining ECE Children's Home Languages in New Zealand* (Doctoral dissertation, Auckland University of Technology).

